

Extraction chromatographic studies of cobalt(II) with aliquat-336

Malay Datta and Uday Sankar Roy*

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan-731 235, West Bengal, India

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Abstract : A selective method has been developed for extraction chromatographic studies of Co^{II} with aliquat-336 (liquid anion exchanger) coated on silica gel as a stationary phase. Quantitative extraction of Co^{II} has been achieved at 6.0–8.0 M HCl. The effects of different acids with varying concentrations, stripping agents, flow rate on extraction and elution have been investigated. Co^{II} has been separated from binary, ternary and quaternary mixture of various metal ions. Selective separation of Co^{II} has been achieved from most of the common transition metals. The proposed method is simple, rapid and selective.

Keywords : Chromatographic studies, cobalt(II), aliquat-336.

In continuation to the earlier studies¹, the results of extraction chromatographic behaviour of Co^{II} on silica gel column impregnated with high molecular weight amine, aliquat-336 from chloride medium are presented in the present investigation. The extracted species in hydrochloric acid of Co^{II} is likely to be [CoCl₄]²⁻.

Results and discussion

The systematic studies on extraction chromatographic behaviour of Co^{II} with aliquat-336, coated on silica gel in different acids at different concentrations showed that Co^{II} is quantitatively extracted in HCl medium in the concentration range 6.0–8.0 M. Incomplete extraction of Co^{II} has been observed in HNO₃ and H₂SO₄ acids medium. 7.0 M HCl gave best extraction result.

Stripping agents : After extraction, in order to select specific stripping agent for quantitative elution of Co^{II} from the column, different concentration of acids such as HNO₃, H₂SO₄, HCl, CH₃COOH; salt solution of NaNO₃ and deionised water were tested. It was observed that quantitative recovery of Co^{II} is possible with 0.05–0.5 M NaNO₃, 0.01–7.0 M HNO₃, 0.001–0.1 M HCl, 0.05–0.5 M CH₃COOH and also with deionised water. Of these eluents, deionised water and 0.5 M NaNO₃ were found to be most suitable and used as eluent for elution of Co^{II} in further steps of experiment.

Separation of Co^{II} from binary mixture : It was possible to separate Co^{II} from several metal ions in binary mixtures by exploiting the differences in acid concentration for extraction and by using selective eluting agents. In binary mixtures with Co^{II} in 1.0 M HCl, Fe^{III}, Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, Ga^{III} and Pd^{II} were extracted into the column but Co^{II} passed through the column. After

extraction Fe^{III} was eluted with 0.1 M NaNO₃, Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Ga^{III} were eluted with deionised water and Pd^{II} was eluted with 6.5 M HNO₃. Binary mixtures containing Co^{II} with Ce^{IV} and Zn^{II} were passed separately through the column at 0.05 M HCl where Ce^{IV} and Zn^{II} were extracted whereas Co^{II} was passed through the column with the mobile phase. Ce^{IV} was eluted with 6.5 M HNO₃ and Zn^{II} was eluted with deionised water. In binary mixtures with Co^{II} in 1.0 M HNO₃ Th^{IV} and Hg^{II} were extracted into the column whereas Co^{II} was passed through the column with the mobile phase. Both Th^{IV} and Hg^{II} were eluted with deionised water. Binary mixtures containing Co^{II} with U^{VI} and Cr^{III} were passed separately through the column at 1.25 M HCl. At this condition Co^{II} passed through the column with the mobile phase whereas U^{VI} and Cr^{III} were extracted. After extraction U^{VI} was eluted with deionised water and Cr^{III} was eluted with 6.5 M HNO₃. Binary separation of Co^{II} and In^{III} was achieved by passing the mixture at 6.5 M HCl into the column, where both the metal ions were extracted. Co^{II} was eluted first with deionised water followed by In^{III} with 0.1 M NaNO₃. After separation, all the metal ions were estimated complexometrically with EDTA using xylenol orange indicator². The results of binary separations are given in Table 1.

Separation of Co^{II} from multicomponent mixture : The proposed method was applied to separate Co^{II} from several ternary and quaternary mixtures and results are presented in Table 2. In almost all the cases quantitative extraction, and separation have been achieved. The elution profile of Co^{II} in multicomponent mixture (for ternary mixtures only) is given in Fig. 1.

Separation of Co^{II}, Fe^{III} and Cr^{III} was achieved by passing the mixture through the column at 1.25 M HCl. Fe^{III} and Cr^{III}

Table 1. Separation of Co^{II} from binary mixtures
Co^{II} taken = 1.38 mg, column : 0.8 × 6.5 cm, flow rate = 1 ml min⁻¹

Metal ion	W _{metal} (mg)		Recovery of Co ^{II} (%)	Eluent used
	Added	Recovered		
Fe ^{III}	1.94	1.95	100.5	0.1 M NaNO ₃
Pb ^{II}	2.36	2.34	99.15	H ₂ O
Cd ^{II}	4.04	4.06	100.5	H ₂ O
Ga ^{III}	1.44	1.45	100.7	H ₂ O
Pd ^{II}	2.66	2.64	99.2	6.5 M HNO ₃
Ce ^{IV}	3.81	3.78	99.2	6.5 M HNO ₃
Zn ^{II}	2.09	2.11	100.9	H ₂ O
Th ^{IV}	2.18	2.17	99.5	H ₂ O
Hg ^{II}	2.85	2.88	101	H ₂ O
U ^{VI}	2.57	2.57	100	H ₂ O
Cr ^{III}	1.14	1.15	100.9	6.5 M HNO ₃
In ^{III}	2.74	2.72	99.3	0.1 M NaNO ₃

were extracted whereas Co^{II} was passed through the column with mobile phase. Fe^{III} was eluted first with 0.1 M NaNO₃ followed by Cr^{III} with 6.5 M HNO₃. Separation of Co^{II}, Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} was achieved by passing the mixture through the column at 1.25 M HCl. Co^{II} was percolated with the mobile phase whereas Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} were extracted. Pb^{II} was eluted with deionised water followed by Cd^{II} with 0.5 M NaNO₃. Separation of Co^{II}, Pb^{II} and Pd^{II} was achieved by passing the mixed solution through the column at 1.25 M HCl. Pb^{II} and Pd^{II} were extracted whereas Co^{II} was percolated with the mobile phase. Pb^{II} was eluted with 1.0 M NH₄Cl followed by Pd^{II} with 6.5 M HNO₃. Separation of Co^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pd^{II} was achieved by passing the mixture through the column at 0.05 M HCl. Both Cd^{II} and Pd^{II} were extracted whereas Co^{II} was passed through the column. Cd^{II} was eluted with 0.5 M NaNO₃ followed by Pd^{II} with 6.5 M HNO₃. Separation of Co^{II}, Ga^{III} and In^{III} was achieved by passing the mixture through the column at 6.5 M HCl. In^{III} and Co^{II} were extracted whereas Ga^{III} was passed through the column. Co^{II} was eluted with deionised water followed by In^{III} with 0.1 M NaNO₃. Co^{II}, U^{VI} and Ce^{IV} were separated by passing the mixture through the column at 0.05 M HCl. Only Ce^{IV} was extracted and the other metal ions were passed through the column with mobile phase. Ce^{IV} was eluted with 6.5 M HNO₃. Mobile phase containing Co^{II} and U^{VI} was again passed through the column at 1.25 M HCl. Co^{II} was percolated with the mobile phase. U^{VI} was extracted and eluted with deionised water. Separation of Co^{II}, Th^{IV} and U^{VI} was achieved by passing the mixed solution through the column at 0.5 M HNO₃ first. Under this condition only Th^{IV} was extracted and both Co^{II} and U^{VI} were passed through the column. Extracted Th^{IV} was eluted with deionised water. Mobile phase containing Co^{II} and U^{VI} was again passed through the column at 1.25 M HCl. Co^{II} was

passed through the column whereas U^{VI} was extracted and eluted with 0.1 M HNO₃. Synthetic mixture containing Co^{II}, Hg^{II} and Zn^{II} was passed through the column at 0.05 M HCl. Hg^{II} and Co^{II} were passed through the column, Zn^{II} was extracted and eluted with deionised water. The mobile phase containing Co^{II} and Hg^{II} was again passed through the column at 1.0 M HNO₃. Under this condition Co^{II} was percolated with the mobile phase whereas Hg^{II} was extracted and the same was eluted with 0.1 M NaNO₃.

Table 2. Separation of Co^{II} from multicomponent synthetic mixtures
Column = 0.8 × 6.5 cm, flow rate = 1 ml min⁻¹

Sl. no.	Metal ions in mixture	W _{added} (mg)	Recovery (%)	Relative error (%)	Eluent used	V _{Eluent} (ml)
1.	Co ^{II}	1.38	100	00	-	25
	Fe ^{III}	1.94	99.6	-0.51	0.1 M NaNO ₃	30
	Cr ^{III}	1.14	99.1	-0.87	6.5 M HNO ₃	30
2.	Co ^{II}	1.38	99.3	-0.72	-	20
	Pb ^{II}	2.36	99.6	-0.42	H ₂ O	30
	Cd ^{II}	4.04	100.5	+0.49	0.5 M NaNO ₃	25
3.	Co ^{II}	1.38	100	00	-	25
	Pb ^{II}	2.36	99.1	-0.85	1.0 M NH ₄ Cl	30
	Pd ^{II}	2.66	99.2	-0.75	6.5 M HNO ₃	25
4.	Co ^{II}	1.38	100	00	-	20
	Cd ^{II}	4.04	99.5	-0.49	0.5 M NaNO ₃	30
	Pd ^{II}	2.66	100.1	-1.13	6.5 M HNO ₃	25
5.	Co ^{II}	1.38	100.7	+0.72	H ₂ O	30
	Ga ^{III}	1.44	98.6	-1.39	-	25
	In ^{III}	2.74	99.2	-0.73	0.1 M NaNO ₃	30
6.	Co ^{II}	1.38	100	00	-	20
	Fe ^{III}	1.94	100.5	+0.51	0.1 M NaNO ₃	25
	Zn ^{II}	2.09	100.5	+0.48	H ₂ O	30
7.	Co ^{II}	1.38	100	00	-	20
	U ^{VI}	2.57	99.2	-0.78	H ₂ O	30
	Ce ^{IV}	3.81	99.7	-0.26	6.5 M HNO ₃	25
8.	Co ^{II}	1.38	98.5	-1.45	-	25
	Th ^{IV}	2.18	100	00	H ₂ O	30
	U ^{VI}	2.57	99.2	-0.78	0.1 M HNO ₃	30
9.	Co ^{II}	1.38	98.5	-1.45	-	20
	Hg ^{II}	2.85	99.3	-0.70	0.1 M NaNO ₃	25
	Zn ^{II}	2.09	100.5	+0.48	H ₂ O	25
10.	Co ^{II}	1.38	100.7	+0.72	-	20
	Fe ^{III}	1.94	100	00	0.1 M NaNO ₃	30
	Cr ^{III}	1.14	101.7	+1.75	6.5 M HNO ₃	25
11.	Zn ^{II}	2.09	98.5	-1.43	H ₂ O	30
	Co ^{II}	1.38	100	00	-	25
	Zn ^{II}	2.09	100.5	+0.48	H ₂ O	30
	Cd ^{II}	4.04	100.5	+0.49	0.5 M NaNO ₃	30
	Hg ^{II}	2.85	98.6	-1.40	0.05 M Na ₂ SO ₄	25

Fig. 1. Separation of Co^{II} from synthetic multicomponent mixture.

Separation of synthetic quaternary mixture containing Co^{II} , Fe^{III} , Cr^{III} and Zn^{II} was achieved by passing the mixture through the column at 0.05 M HCl first, where only Zn^{II} was extracted and the same was eluted with deionised water. The mobile phase containing Co^{II} , Fe^{III} and Cr^{III} was again passed through the column at 1.25 M HCl . Under this condition Fe^{III} and Cr^{III} was extracted and Co^{II} was percolated with the mobile phase. Fe^{III} was eluted with 0.1 M NaNO_3 followed by Cr^{III} with 6.5 M HNO_3 . Separation of Co^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} was achieved by passing the mixture through the column at 0.05 M HCl . At this condition Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} were extracted whereas Co^{II} and Hg^{II} were passed through the column. Zn^{II}

was eluted with deionised water followed by Cd^{II} with 0.5 M NaNO_3 . The mobile phase containing Co^{II} and Hg^{II} was again passed through the column at 1.0 M HNO_3 . Co^{II} was percolated with the mobile phase whereas Hg^{II} was extracted and it was eluted with $0.05\text{ M Na}_2\text{SO}_4$.

Experimental

An Elico LI-120 pH meter with a combined glass electrode and a chromatographic column (Borosil) were used.

The liquid anion exchanger, aliquat-336 (Fluka, AG), a high molecular mass synthetic quaternary ammonium compound (tricaprylmethylammonium chloride) was used as such. A stock solution of Co^{II} (1.38 mg ml^{-1}) was prepared by dissolving cobalt(II) chloride (CoCl_2) in distilled water and standardised complexometrically using xylenol orange indicator². The ion exchange material was prepared following literature method³.

Extraction procedure : 7.0 M HCl (20 ml) was passed through the column ($0.8 \times 6.5\text{ cm}$). An aliquot containing 1.38 mg of Co^{II} was passed through the column (7.0 M HCl) at a flow rate 1 ml min^{-1} . After extraction, Co^{II} was stripped with different acids, bases and salts of various concentrations and deionised water. Deionised water and 0.5 M NaNO_3 solution were found to be the best stripping agent. The amount of Co^{II} was determined complexometrically.

Exchange capacity : The exchange capacity of the exchanger was determined at different temperatures ($20\text{--}40\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) measuring milligram equivalents of OH^- absorbed by 1 g of dry exchanger in the chloride form⁴. The liberated chloride was titrated against standard AgNO_3 solution using potassium chromate as indicator⁵. The exchange capacity was found to be 0.57 meq g^{-1} dry exchanger.

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